

CHEMICAL REACTION EFFECT ON MASS TRANSFER IN THE PRESENCE OF THERMAL RADIATION

A S HARIPRASAD*

PRUTHVIRAJ R D**

*Department of Mathematics,Rajarajeswari College of Engineering,Bangalore,Karnataka,INDIA

***Department of Cemistry,Rajarajeswari College of Engineering,Bangalore,Karnataka,INDIA

ABSTRACT:

The present work is concerned with the analytical solutions of the unsteady mass transfer flow past a semi-infinite vertical porous plate embedded in a porous medium with heat source. The influence of chemical reaction is taken into account. The governing equations are solved by perturbation technique. The effects of different pertinent parameters on velocity temperature, concentration are discussed with the help of graphs and tables. The results of the present study agree well with the previous solutions. Applications of the present study are shown in material processing systems and different chemical industries.

Keywords: Chemical reaction, Thermal radiation, Porosity, Heat source.

INTRODUCTION

Magnetohydrodynamics is the study of flow of electrically conducting fluids in electric and magnetic fields. This phenomenon is essentially one of the mutual interaction between the fluid velocity and electromagnetic field i.e. the motion of the fluid affects the magnetic field and the magnetic field affects the fluid motion. Basically, magnetohydrodynamics is a research area that involves the study of motion of electrically conducting fluids such as plasma and salt water. MHD flows are found to have influential applications in many natural and man made flows. MHD flow with combined heat and mass transfer have several important applications in variety of engineering processes including heat exchanger devices, petroleum reservoirs, chemical catalytic reactors, ceramic materials, migration of moisture through air contained in fibrous insulations and grain storage installations and the dispersion of chemical contaminants through water saturated soil, super convecting geothermic etc.. The literature on the study of MHD flow with heat and mass transfer is abundant. Some of these are given here. Lai and Kulachi [1] used the series expansion method to investigate coupled heat and mass transfer in natural convection from a sphere in a porous medium. The heat and mass transfer effects on a flow along a vertical plate in the presence of magnetic field

was investigated by Elbashbeshy [8]. The influence of combined natural convection from a vertical wavy surface due to thermal and mass diffusion was studied by Hossain and Rees [9]. Chen [6] investigated the effects of heat and mass transfer in MHD free convection from a vertical surface. Soundalgekar [6] presented an exact solution to the flow of a viscous fluid past an impulsively started infinite isothermal vertical plate with mass transfer. Muthucumaraswamy and Ganesan [7] have studied numerical solution of flow past an impulsively started semi-infinite isothermal vertical plate with uniform mass diffusion. Toki [4] developed the analytical solutions for free convection and mass transfer flow near a moving vertical porous plate. Das [5] developed the closed form solutions for the unsteady MHD free convection flow with thermal radiation and mass transfer near a moving vertical plate. Recently Ahmmed et al. [6] studied the unsteady MHD free convection and mass transfer flow past a vertical porous plate. The effect of chemical reaction on above discussed flow is very useful for improving a number of chemical technologies such as drying, distribution of temperature and moisture over agricultural fields and groves of fruit trees, damage of crops due to freezing, evaporation at the surface of a water body, energy transfer in a wet cooling tower and flow in a desert cooler. Many practical diffusive operations involve the molecular diffusion of a species in the presence of chemical reaction within or at the boundary. Therefore, the study of heat and mass transfer with chemical reaction is of great practical importance to engineers and scientists. Raji Reddy and Srihari [6] studied numerical solution of unsteady flow of a radiating and chemically reacting fluid with time-dependent suction. Venkateswarlu and Satyanarayana [7] have studied the effects of chemical reaction and radiation absorption on the heat and mass transfer flow of nano fluid in a rotating system. Chamber and Young (1958) analyzed the effects of homogeneous 1st order chemical reactions in the neighbourhood of a flat plate for destructive and generative reactions. Muthucumaraswamy et al. (2008) have studied the mass transfer effect on isothermal vertical oscillating plate in presence of chemical reaction. Swain et al. (2014) investigated the effect of chemical reaction and thermal radiation on the hydromagnetic free convective rotating flow past an accelerated vertical plate in the presence variable heat and mass diffusion. Das et al. [8] have considered the effects of homogeneous first order chemical reaction on the flow past an impulsively started infinite vertical plate with constant heat flux and mass transfer. Venkateswarlu et al. [30] had presented chemical reaction and radiation absorption effects on the flow and heat transfer of a Nano fluid in a rotating system. A two dimensional unsteady, free convective laminar flow with heat and mass transfer past a semi-infinite vertical

moving plate in a uniform porous medium is considered. It is taken that fluid is incompressible, viscous and electrically conducting. A uniform transverse magnetic field in the presence of pressure gradient is applied to the system. First order chemical reaction, heat generation effect, thermal diffusion and thermal radiation are taken into account. x^* axis is taken along the plate and y^* axis is taken normal to it. It is supposed that there is no applied voltage and induced magnetic field. Also viscous and Darcy resistance terms are assumed to be present. Due to the semi-infinite plate surface assumption, the flow variables are functions of y^* and t^* . Now under the usual Boussinesq approximation, the governing boundary layer equations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To discuss the physical significance of various parameters involved in the results, the numerical calculations have been carried out. The effects of the various parameters entering in the governing equations on the velocity, temperature, skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number are shown through graphs.

Fig1. Velocity profiles for different values of Sc

The fluid velocity increases to a peak value and decreases. The peak value is more distinctive due to increase in species buoyancy force. Velocity distribution attains maximum value in the vicinity of the plate. It is observed that velocity increases with increasing values of solutal Grashoff number. Again the thickness of momentum boundary layer is more for fluid with low Prandtl number. The reason underlying this behavior arises from the fact that the increase in the Prandtl number is due to the increase in the viscosity of the fluid, which makes the fluid thick and hence the fluid moves slowly

Fig.2 Temperature profiles for different values of R

It is seen that the velocity and concentration profiles decrease with increases in the chemical reaction parameter. This shows that the diffusion rates can be tremendously altered by chemical reactions. It is also important to note that increasing the chemical reaction parameter significantly alters the concentration boundary layer thickness without any significant effect on the momentum and thermal boundary layers.

Fig.3 Concentration profiles for different values of Rc

It is inferred that the velocity decreases with increasing Schmidt number. An increasing Schmidt number implies that viscous forces dominate over the diffusion effects. Schmidt number in free convection flow regimes represents the relative effectiveness of momentum and mass transport by diffusion in the velocity (momentum) and concentration (species) boundary layers. Smaller Sc values correspond to lower molecular weight species diffusing in air (eg Helium ($Sc = 0.3$), water vapour ($Sc = 0.6$), ammonia ($Sc = 0.78$),) and higher values to denser hydrocarbons diffusing in air. Therefore an increase in Sc will counteract momentum diffusion since viscosity effects will increase and molecular diffusivity will be reduced. The flow will therefore be decelerated with a rise in Sc. It is observed that an increase in the Prandtl number results a decrease of the thermal boundary layer thickness and in general lower average temperature within the boundary layer. The reason is that smaller values of Pr are equivalent to increase in the thermal conductivity

of the fluid and therefore, heat is able to diffuse away from the heated surface more rapidly for higher values of Pr. Hence, in the case of smaller Prandtl number as the thermal boundary layer is thicker and the rate of heat transfer is reduced. It is noticed that an increase in radiation parameter leads to an increase in the temperature which implies that radiation tends to enhance fluid temperature. It is observed that when S_o increases concentration also increases. It yields a maximum value near the plate and then decreases.

Table-1

Sl. No.	Q	R	Pr	Nu
1	1	2	0.71	2.0113
2	2	2	0.71	2.6694
3	3	2	0.71	3.1780
4	1	3	0.71	2.2770
5	1	4	0.71	2.5103
6	1	2	4.5	6.9088
7	1	2	7	9.6794

Table-1: Variations of Nusselt number Nu are illustrated in this table. It is noticed that increase in Q, R and Pr result an increase in the Nusselt number. Table-3: It presents the numerical values of skin friction (τ) at the plate due to variations in Gr, Gc, Pr, Rc, Sc. It is noticed that skin friction decreases as Rc, Sc and Pr increase. But Gr and Gc enhance the skin friction.

CONCLUSION

A two dimensional unsteady, free convective laminar flow with heat and mass transfer along with chemical reaction past a semi-infinite vertical moving plate in a uniform porous medium is considered. The governing system of equations was solved analytically with the help of Perturbation method. The effects of the parameters on the velocity, concentration, temperature skin friction, Sherwood number were studied in details. Some important conclusions are summarized as follows.

REFERENCES

1. Raji Reddy, S. and K. Srihari (2009)., numerical solution of unsteady flow of a radiating and chemically reacting fluid with time-dependent suction. Indian Journal of Pure and Applied physics 47, 7-11.
2. Venkateswarlu B, Satyanarayana PV. Chemical reaction and radiation absorption effects on the flow and heat transfer of a nano fluid in a rotating system. J Appl Nano Sci 2015; 5:351–60.

3. Chamber, P. L. and Young, J. D. (1958). The effects of homogeneous 1st order chemical reactions in the neighbourhood of a flat plate for destructive and generative reactions. *Physics of Fluids* 1: 48–54.
4. Swain, B. K., Senapati, N., and Dash, M. (2014). The effect of chemical reaction and thermal radiation on the hydromagnetic free convective rotating flow past an accelerated vertical plate in the presence variable heat and mass diffusion. *Der Chemica Sinica* 5(3): 56–66.
5. Muthucumaraswamy, R. and Janakiramana, (2008). Mass transfer effect on isothermal vertical oscillating plate in presence of chemical reaction. *B. Int J. of Appl. Math. and Mech.* 4(1): 59–65.
6. Chien-Hsin-Chen, Combined heat and mass transfer in MHD free convection from a vertical surface with Ohmic heating and viscous dissipation *Int. J. Eng. Science*, 42(2004), 699-713.
7. E.M.A Elbashbeshy, Heat and mass transfer along a vertical plate with variable surface temperature and concentration in the presence of the magnetic field, *Int.J. Eng Sc.* 34, (1997), 515-522.
8. M.A Hossain & D.A.S Rees, Combined heat and mass transfer in natural convection flow from a vertical wavy surface, *Acta.Mech*, 36, (1999), 133-141.
9. F.C Lai & F.A Kulachi, The effects of variable viscosity on convective heat transfer along a vertical surface in a saturated porous medium, *Int J.Heat and mass transfer*, 33, (1990), 1028-1031.
10. Soundalgekar, V. M., Effects of Mass Transfer and free convection on the flow past an impulsively started vertical plate, *ASME J. of Appl. Mechanics*, 46, (1979), 757-760.
11. Das, U. N.; Deka, R. K. and Soundalgekar, V. M., Effects of Mass Transfer on flow past an impulsively started infinite vertical plate with constant heat flux and chemical reaction, *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, 60, (1994), 284-287.
12. C. J. Toki, “Free convection and mass transfer flow near a moving vertical porous plate: an analytical solution,” *Journal of Applied Mechanics, Transactions ASME*, vol. 75, no. 1, Article ID 0110141, 2008.
13. K. Das, “Exact solution of MHD free convection flow and mass transfer near a moving vertical plate in presence of thermal radiation,” *African Journal of Mathematical Physics*, vol. 8, pp. 29–41, 2010.
14. Venkateswarlu, B. and Satya Narayana, P.V. (2015) Chemical Reaction and Radiation Absorption Effects on the Flow and Heat Transfer of a Nanofluid in a Rotating System. *Applied Nanoscience*, 5, 351-360.
15. S. F. Ahmmed, M.K. Das and L.E. Ali, (2015) “Analytical study on unsteady MHD free convection and mass transfer flow past a vertical porous plate”, *American journal of applied mathematics*, vol.3, No.2, pp.64-74.